

Axial Behaviour of Square CFST Columns: A Comprehensive Parametric Study

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ABSTRACT

A parametric study on axially loaded square CFST columns is carried out considering four key parameters: the concrete cylinder strength f'_c , the steel yield stress f_y , the side length of the square section B , and the steel tube thickness t . A total of 108 square CFST column specimens are analysed. In each case, one parameter is varied while the remaining three are kept constant, resulting in four case studies: (1) variation in steel tube thickness, (2) variation in steel yield stress, (3) variation in concrete strength, and (4) variation in cross-sectional size. This paper presents the results of Case I. The parametric study provides essential insights into how these parameters influence the peak load-carrying capacity and overall behaviour of square CFST columns.

Keywords: CFST, Cylinder strength of concrete, Yield stress of steel and Parametric study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Square CFST columns are widely used in modern high-rise structures, bridges, and seismic-resistant construction. The steel tube thickness, concrete strength, steel yield stress, and the size of the square section significantly influence the load-carrying capacity of these columns. Understanding the effect of each parameter is therefore essential for achieving optimal performance and ensuring safe, efficient design. In this study, 108 load–strain curves of square CFST specimens were analysed by varying the steel tube thickness while keeping the other parameters constant. The resulting cases provide valuable insights into the behaviour of square CFST columns and the influence of key parameters on their structural response.

2 METHODS AND MATERIAL

The parametric study of axially loaded square CFST specimens without any stiffeners or internal reinforcement is carried out using the previously developed analytical equation. This equation provides the confined concrete stress, and by combining it with the corresponding steel stress at the same strain level, the load–strain response of the square CFST section can be generated. The material properties adopted for the parametric study are presented below.

The stress-strain model of steel was adopted from Dalin Liu and Wie-Min Gho's research paper. This model was studied and used for the parametric study. The value of Young's modulus of elasticity was taken to be 200000MPa. The value of strain in steel corresponding to the yield stress of steel was obtained by dividing the yield stress by the modulus of elasticity of steel.

Fig. 1. Liu and Gho Model of steel.

Fig. 2. Cross section of square CFST column.

Through varying above given four parameters total 108 number of possible square CFST column specimens can be formed. The procedure to obtain the Load-strain curve for any square CFST is given below:

$$y = \frac{1100x}{1+500x+95000x^2} \times f'_c \tag{1}$$

The confined concrete stress–strain relationship is obtained using the devised Equation (1), where y represents the confined concrete stress, x is the corresponding strain, and f'_c is the concrete cylinder strength. Using this equation, the confined concrete stress is calculated for any chosen strain value.

The stress in confined concrete is defined as $\sigma_c = \frac{P_c}{A_c}$ (2)

which gives the load carried by concrete as $P_c = \sigma_c \times A_c$ (3)

where A_c is the area of concrete.

Similarly, using the steel stress–strain model, the steel stress σ_s is obtained for the same strain level. The load carried by the steel tube is then

$$P_s = \sigma_s \times A_s \quad (4)$$

where A_s is the steel area.

The total axial load carried by the square CFST section is the sum of the concrete and steel contributions:

$$P = P_s + P_c \quad (5)$$

where P is the axial capacity of the square CFST specimen.

Table 1. Material and geometric properties of specimens for validation

Reference	Specimen	B×B (mm×mm)	t (mm)	$\frac{D}{t}$	f'_c (MPa)	f_y (MPa)
Liang <i>et al.</i> (2006)	S1	127×127	3.15	55.45	30.5	356
Ouyang and Kwan (2018)	CR4-A-4-1	148×148	4.38	33.78	40.5	262
	CR8-C-8	175×175	6.47	27.04	77	835
Qing Quan Liang (2009)	I-A	100×100	2.29	43.7	38.4	197

Figs. 3 Validation of curve obtained from proposed model and curve obtained experimentally.

Fig. 3 show good agreement between the the load strain behaviour obtained using proposed model are well followed the load strain behaviour under same axial load for the same specimen.

Table 2. Material and geometric properties of parametric study specimens

Three sizes of square section (mm) taken	Four types of thicknesses of (mm) are taken	Three sizes of square section (mm) taken	Three different yield strengths (f_y) (MPa) of steel taken	Three different strengths (f'_c) (MPa) of concrete taken
100	3	100	250	30
200	4	200	350	50
300	5	300	450	80
-	6	-	-	-

The specimens are named as follows:

$$f'_c - f_y - B - t$$

$$50 - 250 - 100 - 3$$

Table 3. Nomenclature of square CFST column specimens

Name of specimen	Group identification	Name of specimen	Group identification	Name of specimen	Group identification
30-250-100-3	A1	50-250-100-3	J1	80-250-100-3	S1
30-250-100-4	A2	50-250-100-4	J2	80-250-100-4	S2
30-250-100-5	A3	50-250-100-5	J3	80-250-100-5	S3
30-250-100-6	A4	50-250-100-6	J4	80-250-100-6	S4
30-250-200-3	B1	50-250-200-3	K1	80-250-200-3	T1
30-250-200-4	B2	50-250-200-4	K2	80-250-200-4	T2
30-250-200-5	B3	50-250-200-5	K3	80-250-200-5	T3
30-250-200-6	B4	50-250-200-6	K4	80-250-200-6	T4
30-250-300-3	C1	50-250-300-3	L1	80-250-300-3	U1
30-250-300-4	C2	50-250-300-4	L2	80-250-300-4	U2
30-250-300-5	C3	50-250-300-5	L3	80-250-300-5	U3
30-250-300-6	C4	50-250-300-6	L4	80-250-300-6	U4
30-350-100-3	D1	50-350-100-3	M1	80-350-100-3	V1
30-350-100-4	D2	50-350-100-4	M2	80-350-100-4	V2
30-350-100-5	D3	50-350-100-5	M3	80-350-100-5	V3
30-350-100-6	D4	50-350-100-6	M4	80-350-100-6	V4
30-350-200-3	E1	50-350-200-3	N1	80-350-200-3	W1
30-350-200-4	E2	50-350-200-4	N2	80-350-200-4	W2
30-350-200-5	E3	50-350-200-5	N3	80-350-200-5	W3
30-350-200-6	E4	50-350-200-6	N4	80-350-200-6	W4
30-350-300-3	F1	50-350-300-3	O1	80-350-300-3	X1
30-350-300-4	F2	50-350-300-4	O2	80-350-300-4	X2
30-350-300-5	F3	50-350-300-5	O3	80-350-300-5	X3
30-350-300-6	F4	50-350-300-6	O4	80-350-300-6	X4
30-450-100-3	G1	50-450-100-3	P1	80-450-100-3	Y1
30-450-100-4	G2	50-450-100-4	P2	80-450-100-4	Y2
30-450-100-5	G3	50-450-100-5	P3	80-450-100-5	Y3
30-450-100-6	G4	50-450-100-6	P4	80-450-100-6	Y4
30-450-200-3	H1	50-450-200-3	Q1	80-450-200-3	Z1
30-450-200-4	H2	50-450-200-4	Q2	80-450-200-4	Z2
30-450-200-5	H3	50-450-200-5	Q3	80-450-200-5	Z3
30-450-200-6	H4	50-450-200-6	Q4	80-450-200-6	Z4
30-450-300-3	I1	50-450-300-3	R1	80-450-300-3	AA1
30-450-300-4	I2	50-450-300-4	R2	80-450-300-4	AA2
30-450-300-5	I3	50-450-300-5	R3	80-450-300-5	AA3
30-450-300-6	I4	50-450-300-6	R4	80-450-300-6	AA4

3. PARAMETERS

A parametric study is conducted by varying the thickness of the square CFST columns while keeping the concrete cylinder strength, steel yield stress, and overall cross-sectional size constant. This allows the influence of steel tube thickness on the behaviour of square CFST columns to be evaluated. The peak load capacities of the specimens are compared to quantify the effect of thickness variation on axial capacity.

Specimens A1, A2, A3, and A4 form one series. The peak load of each specimen is compared with that of A1, the reference specimen of the series. The peak load values are the load carrying capacity of individual square CFST column under axial compression are shown in Fig. 3 to fig. 11.

Similar calculations are performed for all remaining series. The bar chart for Series A to C is presented below.

Fig. 3. Peak load carrying capacity for A B and C series.

Fig. 4. Peak load carrying capacity of D, E and F series.

Fig. 5. Peak load values for G, H and I series specimens

Fig. 6. Peak load values for J, K and L series specimens

Fig. 7. Peak load values for M, N and O series specimens.

Fig. 8. Peak load values for P, Q and R series specimens.

Fig. 9. Peak load values for S, T and U series specimens.

Fig. 10. Peak load values for V, W and X series specimens.

Fig. 11. Peak load values for Y, Z and AA-series specimens.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. This study shows that the peak load-carrying capacity of square CFST columns is strongly influenced by steel tube thickness, concrete cylinder strength, steel yield strength, and the size of the square cross-section.
2. Increasing the steel tube thickness from 3 mm to 6 mm consistently enhanced the axial capacity, with the most significant improvement (58.23%) observed in the smaller 100 mm sections of the G series.

3. Larger sections, such as 300 mm, exhibited diminishing returns, with only a 7.65% increase in the U series.
4. Higher concrete strength (80 MPa) improved load capacity, while lower-strength concrete (30 MPa) benefited more from confinement, showing greater relative enhancement.
5. Increasing the steel yield strength from 250 MPa to 450 MPa resulted in substantial capacity gains, especially in smaller 100 mm sections (58.23% in the G series), whereas the effect was less pronounced in larger 300 mm sections (13.46% in the L series).

References

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